

Natural dyes as neutralization indicators—a short review[†]

A. K. Indrayan

Department of Chemistry, Gurukula Kangri University, Harwar-249 404, India

E-mail : akindray@sancharnet.in

Manuscript received 12 November 2002

Some of the naturally occurring coloured substances are pH-sensitive giving distinctly different colours in acid and basic mediums. Some of them, like the red cabbage aqueous extract, are colour-sensitive even to the same medium pH variation also and make a very good laboratory experiment for pH determination. Anthocyanidins are among the commonly occurring natural pigments. Natural colours giving a sharp, distinct and stable colour change on a change of acid to alkaline medium may be used as acid-alkali indicators in volumetric titrations. Extracts from brazilwood (*Caesalpinia sappan*), ratanjot (*Arnebia nobilis*) and heartwood of jack tree (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*) are found satisfactory natural indicators for much better range than what is provided by conventional acid-base indicators phenolphthalein and methyl orange. Active constituents and structural changes are also discussed.

Natural dyes comprise those colorants (dyes and pigments) that are obtained from animal or vegetable matter without chemical processing¹. More than ninety natural dyes are listed in colour index (I. Natural) comprising about 31 red, 28 yellow, 13 brown, 7 orange, 6 black, 5 green and 3 blue. The natural organic dyes and pigments cover a wide range chemical classes, viz. ketones, quinones, imines, polymethines, naphthaquinones, anthraquinonoids, flavones, flavanols, flavanones, indigoids, chlorophyll, dihydropyrans, anthocyanidins, carotenoids etc. In some cases they are diarylmethanes or in some cases alkaloids also. Among them anthocyanidins are the main. They are the flavonoids, soluble in water and alcohol, and can be extracted² by chopping and macerating the plant material, soaking it for a few minutes in hot water or rubbing alcohol. They impart colour to petals, leaves, roots, and tubers and provide a natural sun-screen to protect against ultraviolet radiation³.

Many of the natural dyes have different colours at different pHs. The earliest definition of acids was given in 1663 by Robert Boyle based upon the natural dye colour changing property on a change in pH, when he stated that acids turned plant juices red. In his book Boyle⁴ described the making of indicator paper from the juice of roses, brazilwood, cochineal and litmus etc. Among the coloured naturally occurring substances having a colour changing property on a change in pH, the commonly known are turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), the extracts of red cabbage (*Brassica oleracea*, *Capitata rosa*)^{3,5}, brazilwood (*Caesalpinia sappan*)⁶, jack tree heartwood (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*)⁷, ratanjot (*Arnebia nobilis*)⁸, fruits of garden nightshade (*Solanum nigrum*)⁹, blueberries (*Vaccinium corymbo-*

sum)¹⁰, yellow onion (*Allium cepa*) skins¹¹, grapejuice (*Vitis labrusca*), beetroot (*Beta vulgaris*)¹² etc. Even the litmus is lichen extract and phenolphthalein used to be an active constituent of Ex-Lax. Even the flower extract of Jungle flame (*Ixora coccinea*)^{13,14} has varied colours at varied pHs. The colours in acid and basic mediums of the important of them alongwith their active constituents are given in Table 1.

Some of them have varied colours even in acid medium itself (different at pH 2, 4 and 6) and/or in basic medium itself (different at pH 8, 10, 12 and 14). Such substances make a very good educational experiment for a pH check in laboratory without the use of expensive pH-meter. The colours of red cabbage aqueous extract make an interesting study^{5,15,16}. It has the following colour variations : pH 2(red), 3(purple), 5(violet), 7(blue), 9(blue-green), 12(green). To make the lab experimnt to be convenient, the solution for different pH may be obtained from household materials also. Six test tubes each containing 1 ml indicator solution (red cabbage aqueous extract; it should be prepared fresh; all natural indicators work best if freshly made) are marked A to F, respectively, for pH 2 to 12 as above. 3 ml each of freshly squeezed lemon juice (pH ≈2), white vinegar (pH ≈3), boric acid solution 1 g/100 ml (pH ≈5), water (pH = 7), sodium bicarbonate solution, 1 g baking soda in 100 mL aqueous solution (pH ≈8), borax solution, 1 g sodium borate in 100 mL aqueous solution (pH ≈9) and sodium carbonate solution (pH ≈12) are added in A to F. Colours in various test tubes are observed.

The term anthocyanin usually denotes the form usually found in nature that contains covalently bound carbohydrates.

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Table 1. Active constituents of some natural dyes that can be used as acid-alkali indicators

Natural substance	One of the active constituents	Colour	
		Acid	Alkali
Brazilwood (heartwood) (<i>Caesalpinia sappan</i>)	Brazilin 	Light yellow	Red
Ratanjot (root) (<i>Arnebia nobilis</i>)	Arnebin-7 	Red	Blue
Jack tree (heartwood) (<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>)	Cycloartocarpesin 	Creamish	Mustard Yellow
Turmeric (rhizome) (<i>Curcuma longa</i>)	Curcumin 	Yellow	Red
Red cabbage (<i>Brassica oleracea</i>) (<i>Capitata rosa</i>)	Cyanidin 	Pink	Green
Blue-berries (<i>Vaccinium corymbosum</i>)	Malvidin 	Red	Green
Yellow onion (skin) (<i>Allium cepa</i>)	Quercetin 	Brownish	Orange
Garden nightshade (fruit) (<i>Solanum nigrum</i>)	Solanin 	Red	Yellow

Thus, anthocyanins are among the glycosides in which the aglycone portion is termed the anthocyanidin. On acid hydrolysis of glycoside the carbohydrate moieties are removed and the anthocyanidin is produced. The anthocyanidins usually contain three rings with conjugated double bonds (Fig. 1)¹⁷. Individual anthocyanins contain differences in the ring B which can be hydroxylated or methoxylated at the 3', 4' and 5' positions. The carbohydrates in naturally occurring anthocyanins usually occur in glycosidic linkages at the 3 and/or 5 positions on ring A. An anthocyanin is termed a diglycoside if it has a carbohydrate moiety at both the 3 and 5 positions.

A plant material may have one or more anthocyanins in it. There appear¹⁸ to be only one anthocyanin (cyanidin) in red cabbage but three (delphinidin, petunidin, malvidin) in blueberries. The red cabbage anthocyanin is apparently a

Fig. 1. Structure of anthocyanin aglycone : pelargonidin R=R'=H, cyanidin R=OH R'=H, delphinidin R=R'=OH, peonidin R=OCH₃ R'=H, petunidin R=OCH₃ R'=OH, malvidin R=R'=OCH₃. In certain others (rosanidine, hirsutidin, apigeninidin, luteolinidin, tricetinidin, auranthinidin, pulchellidin, erupropinidin, capensinidin etc.) the substituents at 3, 5, 6 and/or 7 may also vary.

diglycoside. It is through the work of Brouillard¹⁹ that our current understanding of the pH-induced colour changes of the anthocyanins is based. The anthocyanin exists in dilute acid solutions as a positively charged oxonium ion termed as a flavylium cation (Fig. 2). This results in an extended conjugation of double bonds through the three rings of the anthocyanin and, thus, the absorption of photons in the

Fig. 2. Two forms of anthocyanin aglycone cores responsible for the primary colour change between pH 1 and 5.

visible region of the spectrum. The coloured flavylium cation is in equilibrium with a colourless pseudo-base form, which begins to predominate as the pH of the solution is raised to values greater than three. Curtright et al¹⁷ used the Handerson-Hasselbalch equation to examine the conversion of the acidic (flavylium cation) form of anthocyanins to the less acidic (pseudo-base) form of anthocyanins. Structures of cyanidin at pH 3, 8 and 11 are given in Fig. 3²⁰.

All natural dyes may not be used as indicators in volumetric estimation through acid-alkali titrations, though many of them may have different colours at different pH. Not all of the above (Table 1) pH sensitive natural colours are found to be good acid-alkali indicators because an

Fig. 3. Structures of cyanidin at pHs 3, 8 and 11.

indicator should have a distinct, sharp and stable colour change and not gradual. Looking to the ideal conditions of acid-base indicators, the extracts from (i) brazilwood, (ii) heartwood of jack tree and (iii) roots of ratanjot seem to be the best. A thorough study of the use of extract of brazilwood has been carried out⁶. The semisolid red-brown dye is isolated²¹ by extracting the heartwood in ethanol. 1 g of dye is dissolved in 100 ml of 95% ethanol to prepare the indicator solution; it has a pH of 5.4. Volumetric titrations are carried out with four different solutions of acids and bases (0.01, 0.1, 1.0 and 4.0 N). Strong acid with strong base (HCl/NaOH), strong acid with weak base (HCl/NH₄OH) and weak acid with strong base (CH₃COOH/NaOH) are titrated. The pH-metric titrations are also performed in each case. The reproducibility is better than +3%. A comparison with the conventional indicators phenolphthalein and methyl orange is also made. Results of pH-metric titrations are summarised in Table 2.

Vol. of acid or alkali taken = 25ml. [Acid] = 1.0N, [Alkali] = 1.0N				
Type of titration	Volume of alkali added ml.	pH	Colour	Colour change
Strong acid-strong base	24.80	2.80	Light pink	Sharp
	24.95	4.85	Yellow	Sharp
	25.00	8.06	Red	Sharp
Strong acid-weak base	24.80	2.38	Light pink	Sharp
	24.90	5.30	V. light yellow	Sharp
	25.00	6.15	Light pink	Sharp
Weak acid-strong base	23.40	5.97	Light yellow	Gradual
	24.80	6.80	Orange	Sharp
	25.00	9.63	Pink red	

The results (Table 2) indicate two stages of the colour change. It is explained on the basis of three structures (I, II and III) and is supported by obtaining of two types of λ_{\max} values (325 and 540 nm) in the solution at equivalence point. A successful titration of 10⁻² N acid-alkali could be performed by the natural dye whereas this could not give a satisfactory end-point when phenolphthalein was used. Also the reverse titration in 4 N acid-alkali could be performed by natural dye only and phenolphthalein failed in this range. Moreover, while phenolphthalein fails in strong acid-weak base and methyl orange fails in weak acid-strong base, this natural indicator is successful in strong acid-weak base as well as in weak acid-strong base in most of the tried ranges, barring a few reverse titrations.

In the case of phenolphthalein, in presence of dilute alkali, the lactone ring opens²² and the triphenylcarbinol structure undergoes loss of water to produce the resonating ion, which is red. But in excess alkali the red colour disappears owing to the conversion to benzenoid structure. In the case of *C. sappan*, the main active coloured ingredient is brazilin (I) which is a bit comparable to phenolphthalein. Pure brazilin is also isolated using the method described by Hikino *et al*²³. This dye is light yellow in leuco form but red in quinonoid form. It seems that a change from quinonoid form to benzenoid form in excess alkali as in phenolphthalein, does not take place in the case of brazilin. In weakly acidic medium brazilin exists in its leuco form (I). In alkaline medium the oxidation to quinonoid form brazilin

Table 4. pH-metric titrations

Vol. of acid or alkali taken = 15ml. [Acid] = 1.0N. [Alkali] = 1.0N

Type of titration	Volume of alkali added ml.	pH	Colour	Colour change
Strong acid-strong base	24.95	3.30	Creamish	Sharp
	25.00	9.36	Mustard yellow	Sharp
Strong acid-weak base	24.95	4.07	Creamish	Sharp
	25.00	7.42	Mustard yellow	Sharp
Weak acid-strong base	24.95	6.21	Creamish	Sharp
	25.00	9.54	Mustard yellow	Sharp

quinonoid structure in dihydric phenolic ring but in acid medium it is creamish because of existence of VI. λ_{\max} are 324 and 335 nm.

The results indicate only a single stage of colour change like the phenolphthalein, methyl orange and arnebin-7 but unlike the brazilin.

References

- M. L. Gulrajani and D. Gupta, "Natural Dyes and their Application to Textiles", IIT, Delhi, 1992, p.1.
- Anon., *J. Chem. Educt.*, 1997, **74**, 1176A.
- T. Swain in "Chemistry and Biochemistry of Plant Pigments", ed. T. W. Goodwin Academic, London, 1976, pp. 425-463.
- R. Boyle, "Experiments upon Colours", 1663.
- M. Forster, *J. Chem. Educt.*, 1978, **55**, 107.
- A. K. Indrayan and B. S. Guleria, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 476.
- A. K. Indrayan, R. K. Shukla and R. Kumar, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1999, **11**, 141.
- A. K. Indrayan and V. Yadav, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1999, **11**, 611.
- L. A. Ramos, K. O. Luptz, E. T. G. Cavelheiro and F. Fatibello, *Ecleptica Quim.*, 2000, **25**, 229.
- J. Chandrasekaran, *Resonance*, 2001, 66.
- www.science.csustan.edu/persona/2000/2002-AcidBase.htm
- "LFRA Ingredients Handbook : Food Colours", Leatherhead Food Research Agency, 1997.
- V. Cobb, "Science Experiments You Can Eat", Harper Trophy, USA, 1994.
- J. Tate "Labs Alive", Achimota School, Ghana, 2000.
- R. C. Mebane and T. R. Rybolt, *J. Chem. Educt.*, 1985, **62**, 285.
- C. Borgford and L. Summerlin, "Chemical Activities", American Chemical Society, Washington, DC, 1988, pp. 92-94.
- R. D. Curtright, J. A. Rynearson and J. Markwell, *J. Chem. Educt.*, 1994, **71**, 682.
- R. Curtright, J. A. Rynearson and J. Markwell, *J. Chem. Educt.*, 1996, **73**, 306.
- R. Brouillard, *Phytochem.*, 1983, **22**, 1311.
- G. M. Badgar, "The Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds", Academic, New York, 1961, p. 452.
- B. S. Guleria, A. K. Manav and A. K. Indrayan, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1997, **9**, 816.
- "Vogel's Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th. ed., ELBS, London, 1985.
- H. Hikino, T. Taguchi, H. Fugimura and Y. Hiramatsu, *Planta Med.*, 1977, **31**, 214.
- A. K. Indrayan, V. Yadav and R. Kumar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.
- Y. N. Shukla, J. S. Tandon and M. M. Dhar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 528.
- A. K. Indrayan, R. Kumar and V. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.

